

Structural, Fire, and Energy performance of Cold-Formed Steel Members with Staggered Slotted Perforations: Achievements, Challenges, and Opportunities

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ABSTRACT

Considering the global availability of cold-formed steel (CFS), it serves as a key material for shaping the next generation of sustainable structures in modern construction. CFS with staggered slotted perforations represents a new generation of CFS members that offer enhanced overall performance in terms of structural, fire resistance, and energy efficiency. Therefore, CFS structural members with staggered slotted perforations appear to be a superior choice over conventional CFS members. The staggered slotted perforations in the web offer numerous advantages, such as reducing direct heat transmission across the web and minimising thermal bridging, all of which contribute to a reduction in energy loss in buildings. The application of this new generation of CFS members has gained significant interest within the global construction industry. This paper aims to explore the general state-of-the-art of CFS members with staggered slotted perforations and provide a summary of research conducted on their structural, fire, and energy performance, placing it in a broader context. This paper targets both the research community, aiming to guide future research advancements, and practicing engineers, enabling them to utilize CFS members more readily and confidently with staggered slotted perforations to meet structural, fire, and energy efficiency requirements.

Keywords: Cold-formed steel, Staggered slotted perforations, Structural performance, Fire and thermal performance

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General

Cold-formed steel (CFS) sections offer a combination of strength, cost-effectiveness, design flexibility, and sustainability, making them a sought-after material for a wide variety of construction projects including modular buildings (1, 2). They have various applications in building construction, such as in roof and wall systems, steel racks, structural members for trusses, and other structural elements like columns, beams, and joists (3). CFS members often experience loads and reaction forces, which are prominently designed considering structural aspects. In addition to the main focus on structural design, equal importance has been given to designing light gauge steel buildings considering fire, thermal, energy, and acoustic performance.

The advancement of manufacturing technologies in conjunction with optimisation techniques (4-7) has led innovative CFS profiles that are recommended to enhance the overall performance of buildings. On that note, one of the emerging trends is the new generation of staggered slotted perforated channels in CFS. *Fig. 1* shows the applications of staggered slotted perforated channels in construction. These staggered slotted perforated channels are also known as thermal profiles (8), as they enhance thermal performance.

Fig. 1. Staggered slotted perforated channels in construction (9)

1.2 CFS sections with staggered slotted perforations

CFS members often contain holes in their webs to accommodate service conduits. These web holes typically have conventional shapes, such as circular, square, or rectangular. Recently, a new generation of CFS members with staggered slotted perforations has gained significant attention and commonly used in Nordic countries (10). The staggered rows are arranged in two types: a single row group positioned at the mid-height of the web, or two row groups placed on either side of the mid-height of the web as shown in Fig. 2. The arrangement of slotted perforations in a staggered manner controls thermal bridging across the profile, resulting in enhanced thermal comfort within the indoor building environment. The continuous placement of slotted perforations in a staggered manner increases the complexity of the heat transfer path, whereas in solid web channels, heat is transferred across the web without interruption (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Typical arrangement of staggered web perforations (9, 11)

Fig. 3. Heat flow path in (a) solid web and (b) staggered slotted webs (9)

1.3 Manufacturing process

Different varieties of CFS channels with slotted webs can be found among the selection offered by manufacturers specializing in lightweight construction materials. The slots within the web can be generated through three distinct methods, namely (12) :

- Cutting out slots from the web, resulting in channels with flat web perforations.
- Punching out slots to form bead perforations.
- Employing reticular-stretched slotted perforations, wherein the edges fold inward to create edge stiffeners that enhance resistance.

Advanced manufacturing technologies allow to produce these complex CFS channels with slotted webs. The required manufacturing technology depends on the type of slotted channels. Initially,

slotted perforations are made in the flat steel strips. Subsequently, the perforated steel strips are fed through a sequence of shaped rolls, gradually shaping the section profile. This method results in CFS channels with flat web perforations. Alternatively, slotted perforations can be cut out after the roll forming process to create different types of profiles (12).

1.4 Research focus

While CFS members with staggered slotted perforations have become increasingly popular, there is a notable lack of research findings in the current literature concerning the structural behaviour of these members under axial compression, web crippling, bending, and shear forces, as well as their fire performance and thermal efficiency. Therefore, conducting a comprehensive evaluation to determine the overall performance of CFS staggered slotted perforated members under various conditions is essential for providing optimal design solutions.

Limited research has been conducted to investigate the behaviour of CFS sections, particularly focusing on the influence of staggered slotted perforations on factors such as compression (10, 13, 14), bending (9, 11, 15), web crippling (8, 12, 16), shear (17-20), and combined actions (21). Staggered slotted perforations in the web of a channel section complicate the calculation of the structure's load-bearing capacity (10) while reducing the load-carrying capacity. These investigations have led to the development of design recommendations and guidelines for these new generation of CFS sections. However, there is no established standard design method for staggered slotted perforated members of this type. Existing design methods, such as the AISI S100 (22) and AS/NZS 4600 (23) specifications, focus on channels with conventional discrete openings and do not address continuous staggered perforations found in these profiles. There is limited research available on the thermal efficiency and fire performance evaluation of staggered slotted perforated members. Liu et al. (24) investigated the fire performance of light gauge steel slotted stud walls under ISO 834 standard fire loading. There are a few studies reported in the literature associated with thermal efficiency, including the calculation method for equivalent thermal conductivity (25) and investigations into the thermal performance of slit or slotted web wall studs (26, 27).

This paper initiates the discussion on the effect of staggered slotted perforations on structural members under various loads, as this is crucial for developing a comprehensive understanding of the structural response at the cross-section, member, and frame levels. The fire performance of CFS framed panels made of staggered slotted perforated channels are then discussed in Section 3. Section 4 examines the thermal and energy performance of CFS framed panels constructed with staggered slotted perforated channels and its implications on thermal transmittance (U-value). In Section 5, looking towards the future, the exploration of challenges and opportunities for the application of CFS members with staggered slotted perforations is discussed. This review contributes to a better understanding of the overall behaviour and strength of CFS members with staggered slotted perforations, which is essential for their effective, wider and safe use in construction projects.

2 STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE

2.1 Bending

Degtyarev (15) conducted a review of a limited number of experimental results on staggered slotted CFS beams tested under 4-point bending and uniformly distributed load. Degtyarev (15) emphasized the need for further detailed experimental and numerical studies to gain a comprehensive understanding. Subsequently, Degtyareva et al. (9, 11) investigated the local and distortional buckling failure of staggered slotted CFS beams under bending through detailed numerical studies. They observed a maximum reduction in bending strength of 11% and 23% for local and distortional buckling failure, respectively, compared to solid web beams without perforations.

2.2 Shear

The influence of staggered slotted perforations on the shear strength of CFS beams has been investigated in detail using experimental and numerical analyses (17-20). These studies have shown

that the slotted perforations caused a maximum shear capacity reduction of 71% (17) and an average reduction of 39% in elastic shear buckling strength (18). The reduction in shear strength was more pronounced in channel models with a single perforated region compared to those with two perforated regions (20). Equations were proposed to estimate the shear capacity of slotted perforated channels, both with and without tension field action (20), as well as to estimate the elastic shear buckling strength (19).

2.3 Web crippling

Web crippling is a type of failure that occurs when a CFS beam is subjected to a transverse concentrated load. It has four main types of load case failure modes: End-two flange (ETF), Interior-two flange (ITF), End-one flange (EOF), and Interior-one flange (IOF). Degtyareva et al. (12) and Gatheeshgar et al. (8, 16) investigated these load cases in detail. The staggered slotted perforations caused a reduction in web crippling strength of up to 82% for the ETF load case, 88% for the ITF load case, 74% for the EOF load case, and 49% for the IOF load case compared to solid web channels. The reduction factors mentioned above apply when the flanges are unfastened to the loading and support plates. A detailed investigation is required for the case in which the flanges are fastened to the loading and support plates.

2.4 Combined actions

The presence staggered slotted perforations in the web reduces the combined bending and shear capacity of the CFS beams from 67% to 43% on average when the aspect ratio increased from 1.0 to 4.0 (21). This reduction in combined bending and shear strength may reach the maximum value of 80% compared to the solid web beams (21). Despite the combined bending and shear investigation by Degtyareva et al. (21), the combined bending and web crippling and combined bending and torsion behaviour of staggered slotted perforations have not been investigated yet.

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2.5 Compression

Elastic major flexural buckling of CFS columns with staggered slotted web was investigated by Visy et al. (14). For longer columns with practical slot patterns, a reduction in the critical force due to the slots was observed to be approximately 10–15%. However, for shorter columns, this reduction can exceed 50%. Salhab and Wang (10) proposed equivalent thickness approach addressing the limitations in Kesti (13) to analyse CFS staggered slotted perforated columns under compression. Further detailed investigations are necessary in this field.

2.6 Summary

The presence of staggered slotted perforations in the web of CFS members is clearly associated with a reduction in structural strength. *Fig. 4* illustrates the failure modes of CFS members with staggered slotted perforations under various loading conditions. The extent of this reduction in structural strength varies depending on the type of loading and failure. Many research studies have addressed this by proposing reduction factors to quantify the strength reduction, as summarized in *Table 1*.

Fig. 4. Experimental and numerical failure modes under various loading conditions: (a) Combined bending and shear, (b) Bending-Local buckling, (c) Bending-Distortional buckling, (d) Web crippling-IOF, (e) Web crippling-EOF, (f) Shear, (g) Web crippling -ETF, (h) Web crippling – ITF, and (i) Elastic flexural buckling (8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 21)

Table 1. Proposed reduction factors from research studies

Research study	Failure mode	Proposed reduction factor
Degtyareva et al. (21)	Combined bending and shear	$q_s = \frac{(0.003 \left[\frac{a_1}{d_1}\right]^2 + 0.004 \left[\frac{a_1}{d_1}\right] + 0.078) \left[\frac{d_1}{t}\right]^{0.092} \left[\frac{f_y}{250}\right]^{0.013}}{\left[\frac{L_{sl}}{100}\right]^{0.99} \left[\frac{W_{sl}}{9.5}\right]^{0.43} \left[\frac{N}{n}\right]^{0.068}}$
Degtyareva et al. (11)	Bending (Local buckling)	$q_s = \frac{\left[\frac{B_f}{t}\right]^{2.683} \left[\frac{L_{sl}}{100}\right]^{0.891} \left[\frac{W_{sl}}{9.5}\right]^{0.490} \left[\frac{f_y}{250}\right]^{0.368}}{\left[\frac{D}{t}\right]^{2.132} \left[\frac{B_l}{t}\right]^{0.998} \left[\frac{N}{n}\right]^{0.076}}$
Degtyareva et al. (9)	Bending (Distortional buckling)	$q_s = \frac{\left[\frac{B_l}{B_f}\right]^{1.077} \left[\frac{D}{t}\right]^{0.065} \left[\frac{L_{sl}}{100}\right]^{1.023} \left[\frac{W_{sl}}{9.5}\right]^{0.555} \left[\frac{N}{n}\right]^{0.502}}{\left[\frac{f_y}{250}\right]^{0.004}}$
Gatheeshgar et al. (8)	Web crippling (EOF load case)	$q_s = 1 - 1.30 \frac{\left[\frac{L_{sl}}{100}\right]^{0.487} \left[\frac{nW_{sl}}{d_1}\right]^{0.289} \left[\frac{l_b}{d_1}\right]^{0.203} \left[\frac{d_1}{t}\right]^{0.014} \left[\frac{f_y}{250}\right]^{0.019}}{\left[\frac{r_i}{t}\right]^{0.130}}$
Gatheeshgar et al. (16)	Web crippling (IOF load case)	$q_s = 1 - 10.39 \frac{\left[\frac{L_{sl}}{100}\right]^{0.548} \left[\frac{nW_{sl}}{d_1}\right]^{1.322} \left[\frac{l_b}{d_1}\right]^{0.430}}{\left[\frac{d_1}{t}\right]^{0.183} \left[\frac{r_i}{t}\right]^{0.235} \left[\frac{f_y}{250}\right]^{0.035}}$

Note: The notations used in the equations correspond to those provided in the respective study.

3 FIRE PERFORMANCE

The fire resistance exhibited by CFS wall assemblies with staggered slotted perforated studs differs from that of traditional steel stud walls because of variations in temperature development. Liu et al.(24) investigated the fire performance of non-load-bearing CFS framed partition wall panels made of staggered slotted perforated studs, conducting experiments and numerical studies. Four full-scale fire tests were conducted to obtain failure modes and temperature distribution, with the ISO 834 standard fire loading applied to the wall assemblies. The tested wall assemblies had the dimensions of 1800 mm × 3000 mm with 600 mm stud spacing. The ratio of the total height of slots to the web height was optimised to 50%. The details of the tested specimens and the test results including failure time and failure criteria are presented in *Table 2*. The typical failure modes observed from the fire tests are depicted in *Fig. 5*. Fire resistance of the tested specimens was determined based on insulation and integrity failure criteria. Testing was terminated when flames spread through cracks in the ambient side gypsum boards, indicating an integrity failure.

Table 2. Details of the tested specimens, fire resistance and failure criteria.

Specimen ID	No. of slot rows	Web height (mm)	Configuration	Fire resistance (min)	Integrity criteria	Insulation criteria (°C)	
						Avg. temp	Max. temp
GS-100	5	100		43	Fail	75.1	94.8
GS-150	7	150		61	Fail	83.8	118.7
GD-100	5	100		70	Fail	40.4	44.4
MS-100	5	100		70	Fail	40	41.1

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Fire test failure modes observed: (a) Spalling of gypsum board on exposed surface and (b) Buckling of staggered slotted stud.

Liu et al. (24) employed a numerical parametric study, using validated finite element (FE) models, to investigate the impact of several parameters, including the arrangement of slot rows in the stud web. *Fig. 6(a)* displays the 3D FE model created with appropriate thermal material properties. The impact of slot rows in the stud web on fire performance was investigated by varying the number of slot rows from 0 to 6, and the temperature development on the unexposed side was observed, as illustrated in *Fig. 6(b)*. Observing the results, it is evident that the number of slots has a more pronounced impact on the temperature of the unexposed side. Additionally, Liu et al. (24) concluded that a 50%

perforation ratio was optimal, as there was no significant difference observed in the temperature curve between 50% ($n=5$) and 60% ($n=6$). The presence of staggered slotted perforations improves the fire performance of non-load bearing CFS framed partition wall panels.

Fig. 6. (a) Developed FE model and (b) parametric study results of ambient side time-temperature profile with different number of slot rows.

4 THERMAL AND ENERGY PERFORMANCE

4.1 General

The heat loss through external wall assemblies accounts for 70% of the overall thermal losses in buildings (28). The major challenge lies in minimising thermal bridging across the wall studs due to higher thermal conductivity of steel (29, 30). The staggered slotted perforations mitigate thermal bridging in the CFS channel, improving thermal transmittance (U-values).

4.2 Thermal efficiency assessment

Yang et al. (31) investigated the influence of staggered slotted web on the thermal efficiency of light gauge steel wall panels using hot box tests and FE simulation. The tested wall configuration was designed with staggered slotted perforated studs, fibre cement pressure (FCP) plates serving as the covering plates on both sides, and rock wool used as cavity insulation. Fig. 7(a) illustrates the wall assemblies prepared for testing prior to the attachment of FCP plates. The testing employed the calibrated hot-box method, with the test device operating based on the principle of one-dimensional steady thermal transfer. A total of 11 specimens were tested by varying parameters such as the height of the stud web, stud thickness, parameters of the web slots (Length and width), and stud spacing. The test results (U-values) were compared to those of the reference test specimen with solid web studs, revealing a significant improvement in the U-value around 39%.

Fig. 7. (a) Wall assemblies with rock wool cavity insulation, and (b) a schematic diagram of the finite element model with applied boundary conditions (31)

Yang et al. (31) also developed thermal FE models incorporating suitable thermal parameters for materials, meshing schemes, and boundary conditions, which were then validated against the test results. In Fig. 7(b), the schematic diagram of the finite element model for the wall assembly with

thermal boundary conditions is presented. Subsequently, the validated thermal FE model was further utilized for parametric analysis. This analysis focused on key factors such as the number of slot rows, slot length, slot width, and longitudinal and transverse spacing of the slots, as reviewed herein. *Fig. 8* illustrates the variation of U-values (thermal transfer coefficients) with key parameters associated with slot configuration for different stud thicknesses. It was observed that increasing the number of slot rows and slot length reduces the U-value, thus enhancing the thermal efficiency of the wall assembly. Conversely, increasing the longitudinal and transverse spacing of the slots decreases the U-value, negatively impacting the thermal efficiency of the wall assembly. Yang et al. (31) reported that the width of the slot has minimal influence on the U-values of the wall assembly.

Fig. 8. Influence of (a) the number of slot rows, (b) slot length, (c) longitudinal spacing of the slots, and (d) transverse spacing of slots on U-values.

According to Yang et al. (31), a recommendation for achieving optimal thermal efficiency in an actual project includes the following specifications: Ideally, aim for 5–7 rows of slots, each slot measuring 70–80 mm in length, spaced apart transversely by 6–8 mm. Additionally, the studs should have a thickness of either 1 mm or 1.2 mm, with a distance between each stud of 600 mm.

5 CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Challenges and opportunities lie ahead in the application of staggered slotted perforated profiles in CFS framed structures. Firstly, understanding their structural performance remains a crucial challenge, as their presence notably reduces structural strength, and the continuous nature of perforations may lead to localized failures. Therefore, the development of design standards for these profiles presents an opportunity for advancing their use in construction. Moreover, staggered slotted perforated profiles have greater potential in enhancing fire and thermal performance. Optimizing the dimensions of these perforations, while considering structural, fire, and thermal energy performance, would lead to a balanced overall improvement. Additionally, optimising manufacturing processes to efficiently produce these complex profiles can enhance their accessibility and affordability. Addressing these challenges and seizing these opportunities will contribute to the wider and more effective utilization of staggered slotted perforated profiles in CFS framed structures, ultimately promoting sustainable construction practices.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This review has offered a comprehensive overview of the achievements, challenges, and opportunities linked to the use of cold-formed steel (CFS) members with staggered slotted perforations. Through an examination of their structural, fire, and thermal energy performance, the potential of these members to enhance the overall sustainability and efficiency of building construction has been highlighted. Staggered slotted perforated CFS members present notable advantages in certain construction applications, such as enhancing fire and thermal energy performance. However, their reduced structural strength necessitates ongoing research to accurately estimate the extent of the strength reduction, enabling more efficient structural design. Further efforts are needed to develop construction guidelines for utilizing staggered slotted perforations in structural members. The shift towards more sustainable development is creating new opportunities for incorporating staggered slotted perforated profiles into thermally efficient building construction. Research and development activities are essential to advance these concepts and demonstrate that CFS members with staggered slotted perforations have a unique and enduring contribution to fulfil human needs while preserving the quality of the natural environment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author of this paper wishes to acknowledge the Association of Commonwealth Universities (ACU) for providing an early career conference grant to attend the conference.

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